

The Impact of Hand Hygiene in Infection Control: A Hospital based Study of North Bihar.

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Abstract:

The impact of hand hygiene practices on infection control at Indira Hospital, located in Supaul, Bihar, India. The project aims to reduce Healthcare-Associated Infections (HAIs), enhance patient satisfaction, and enhance hand hygiene protocols. Through a comprehensive methodology including surveys, observational studies, interviews and implementation of PDCA cycle among HCW, the study evaluates current hand hygiene knowledge and practices among healthcare workers (HCWs), identifies barriers to compliance, and implements interventions for improvement. Data analysis reveals there is a positive trend in hand hygiene compliance rates over the last three years, with a concurrent decrease in HAI rates. Despite variations in compliance among different staff categories, overall adherence to hand hygiene protocols shows improvement. Recommendations include implementing of PDCA Cycle in format of continuous training, resource allocation, behavior communication, monitoring and evaluation, promotion of accountability, and provision of incentives and reward to sustain and enhance hand hygiene practices.

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Introduction

Hand hygiene is necessary for a comprehensive understanding and successful execution of hospital infection control practices. It is important measures in preventing hospital acquired infections in health care worker. Here's a breakdown of the required problem statements that's clearly articulates the issue being addressed, which is importance for case study the impact of hand hygiene in infection control at Indira Hospital.

Objectives

Reduce Healthcare-Associated Infections (HAIs): Decrease the rate of incidence healthcare associated infections and improved hand hygiene practices. Enhance Patient Satisfaction: Improve patient satisfaction about cleanliness and knowledge of hand hygiene.

Increase health care worker Compliance: to decrease HAI at target level, we need to increase hand hygiene compliances among hospital staff and implementation of PDCA cycle for improvement of HH compliance rate. Increase hand hygiene compliance among hospital staff, increase staff percentage adherence to hand hygiene practices [1].

Scope of Hand Hygiene in Hospital: The study primarily shows the impact of hand hygiene practices and implementation of PDCA cycle within Indira hospital situated in Supaul, Bihar, India. It

comprises total women care, maternity ward, and IPD and OPD units of the hospital [2].

In-Scope Items: Evaluation of current hand hygiene knowledge and practices among healthcare workers (HCWs) and pts within Indira Hospital. Assessment of the incidence of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) occurring within the hospital. Identification of moments and factor that influence hand hygiene compliance among HCWs, including their knowledge, attitudes, and available resource [3]. Comparison between hand hygiene compliance rates and incidence of HAIs within Indira Hospital. Identification of barriers to optimal compliance of hand hygiene adherence among HCWs and pts including Resource constraint. Development and putting interventions according to objective and goal to achieve target and also improving hand hygiene practices, such as CME and training workshop programs, provision of resources, and advocating proper monitoring and evaluation systems. Which shows the impact of hand hygiene on compliance rates and HAI incidence rates. Documentation of all data related to project activity and surveys. [4]

Out-of-Scope Items: Assessment of hand hygiene practices outside of Indira Hospital, camp or in other healthcare facilities available in supaul District.

Limitations: Limited resources availability and infrastructure constraints within the hospital may impact the implementation of interventions. Time constraints may limit the duration and extent of data collection and analysis. Analysis of Datasets: Its identified the correlation between hand hygiene compliance and HAI incidence rates affect specific impact to Indira Hospital in Supaul.

Methodology

The cohort consisted of HCW of Indira hospital ANM ,GNM 25 (NURSING STAFF ;34.7%), Doctors 10 (Consultant and R.M.O = 13.8%) and lab technicians assistant and HR staff (13 ; 18.05%), others Hospital staff (24 33.3%), in this study program. There are 12 (16.6%) males and 60 (83.3%) females. The research is conducting from January to till date going on enrolled into the study and chosen by their willingness to participation. A prospective, questionnaire based survey and observational study is conducting for a period Starting from (January 2024 to April 2024) in maternity care of Indira hospital a secondary patient care, hospital in Supaul District of Bihar , India. A standard protocol prepared on World Health Organization's (WHO's) 5 Moments of Hand Hygiene practices that is used as observing study to measure the compliance of HH in health care workers [5]. All HCWs is observed for HH compliance and audit of HH moments by an infection control nurse who is posted in Indira hospital and supervised by hospital infection control officer by direct observation method or by ICN for a minimum time period of 20 minutes in 24 hours. Here we taken 200 opportunities for calculating compliance and adherence rate. The infection control team plan monthly meetings to review of the collected data. Report of data like HH compliance, interventions, and barriers to implementation is taken in attention and discussing on monthly basis.

Data Collection and Analysis: Surveys questionnaire is distributed to healthcare workers to know their knowledge, attitudes, and practices of hand hygiene. Observational studies is conducted at Indira hospital. It involves directly watching the HH behavior of HCWs by a trained ICN and progress is going on to monitor hand hygiene compliance in various staff hospital. In addition interviews with HCW and Pts is provided the insights into barriers of hand hygiene compliances and adherence. Ethical Considerations: ethical clearance is taken from the administration department. All data collection methods are adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring HCW participant informed consent confidentiality. Surveys questionnaire is distributed among all staff. 72 health care worker taken participation in survey data revealed variations in hand hygiene knowledge and practices among hospital staff. Observational Studies: Observations were conducted in a hospital. Following aspect, we kept in mind while conducting

hand hygiene audit. Opportunity ideally hand hygiene observation has to be done 24 hrs. a day but it's not possible. so, we taken 200 hand hygiene opportunity as WHO recommendations. Duration of the direct observation period should be minimum of 20 minutes per session. With 95% completion achieved. Preliminary finding reports discrepancies in hand hygiene compliance rates among health care worker of the hospital. Interviews with hospital working staff, including hospital administrators and frontline staff, is conducted as planned questionnaire based data collection and trying to solve all related barriers to hand hygiene adherence [6]. Analysis of Collected data: Total staff members: 72.

Total opportunities: 200

Total actions performed completely: 112.

Male doctors: 2

Female doctors: 8

Female nursing staff: 25

Male lab and HR staff: 4

Female lab and HR staff: 9

Male other staff members: 6

Female other staff members: 18

Questionnaire based Survey Results: Initial analysis of data shows that the majority of HCW don't understand the importance of hand hygiene also not adherence to HH moments, so compliance rates vary [7].

We calculate HH Adherence by following formula.

Hand Hygiene adherence rate (HHAR) =

No of times HH followed completely / No of opportunity of HH moments available * 100

Total number of opportunities of hand hygiene: 200

Total number of health workers: 72

Distribution of staff roles: 10 doctors, 25 nursing staff, 13 lab technicians and HR staff, and 24 other staff.

Total hand hygiene adherence rate [8,9] = (Total no. hand hygiene actions performed by all staff / Total number of opportunities for all staff = 112/200

= 56%

For Doctors:

Number of doctors: 10

Total number of opportunities for doctors: 30

Number of hand hygiene actions performed by doctors: 16

HHAR for doctors : 16/30*100 = 53.3%

For Nursing Staff:

Number of nursing staff: 25

Total number of opportunities for nursing staff: 72

Number of complete hand hygiene actions performed by nursing staff: 4

HHAR for nursing staff: $42/72 * 100 = 58.33\%$

For Lab Technicians and HR Staff:

Number of lab technicians and HR staff: 13

Total number of opportunities for lab technicians and HR staff: 35

Number of hand hygiene actions performed by lab technicians and HR staff: 20.

HHAR for Lab technicians and HR staff = $20/35 * 100 = 57.1\%$

For Other Staff:

Number of other staff: 24

Total number of opportunities for other staff: 63

Number of hand hygiene actions performed by other staff: 32

HHAR for other staff = $32/63 * 100 = 50.8\%$

Observational Data analysis and comparison (CHECK):

During analysis of observational data initially we will assess the percentage of overall compliance (HHAR) is 56.5%, Doctor 53.3%, nursing staff 58.33% , lab technicians and HR staff 57.1 % and other staff 50.8%

This will indicate that whether hand hygiene compliance are higher among hospital health care worker in our hospital compared to others hospital staff such as HR staff and Pharmacy staff. We will also compare our data to that of other hospitals and international research data. We will also analyse the effect of hand hygiene impact on reduction of HAI by comparing hospital previous data through introduction of a Hand hygiene audit.

Figure 1: HHAR rate in all category staff of Indira Hospital

We compare the over hand hygiene compliance percentage with old year data that is 2023, 2022 and 2021, which is around 49%, 45%, 40%.

Also, we found that HAI rate on respective year was 4.3%, 4.5%, 5%. This year we found hand hygiene compliance is 56% in first quarter n also we found that from hospital data the HAI rate is around 4.01%.

Figure 2: HH Compliance percentage

The hand hygiene compliance has shown a steady increase all consecutive years, indicating an improvement in adherence to hand hygiene protocols among staff members [10]

Figure 3: Hospital Acquired Infection (HAI) rate.

The HAI rates have been gradually decreasing in consecutive year, which is a positive trend in decreasing infection. [11] This decrease suggests that the improved hand hygiene compliance might be contributing to the reduction of healthcare-associated infections [12].

Administrative staff Interviews: Analysis of HR staff interviews show they are common barriers to hand hygiene adherence, because lack of awareness and resource allocation

4. Resource Requirements and their availability

Human Resources: Skilled researcher like infection control nurse, infection control officer, skilled worker has knowledge of static is required for data collection and analysis. [13]

Required skilled nurse who collect questionnaire-based survey data.

Human resource is required according to project to audit and observe the hand hygiene moment.

Replacement of ICN Is necessary for unavailability or leave for smoothness of data collection and project progress.

Proper resources Allocation: Hand washing liquid: soap and water is most basic requirement for hand hygiene practice. it should be liquid based and easily available in ward and hospital premise. 40 second for hand washing with soap and water during all 5 moments of HH [14].

Hand sanitizer: We can also use alcohol-based hand sanitizers in replacement of soap water.

Training: proper training and education is requirement for all health care worker and pts for proper function of project. It can be given in the form of CME and workshop of hand hygiene.

Proper hand washing area: there should be availability of proper hand washing area assigned for HH in ward and around hospital premises. So, they can easily do the hand hygiene practices.

Ethical clearance: for proper and smooth functioning ethical clearance is required from the administrative department.

Risks and Mitigations

Following risk is identified during project.

Compliance of Health Care Worker: During initial phase of project there was limited participation of health care worker. but continue motivation and charismatic leadership approach of infection control officer ICO and ICN this risk is mitigated.

Data Collection: Proper Questionnaire based data collection is very much important for successfulness of project. for this there is reward based data management provision reduces risk and giving knowledge and importance of data and its relevancy by ICN.

Resistance to Project: Initially there was resistance for project and use of human resource for project. But proper communication, training, motivation, education this risk is mitigated. Health care worker embrace the project and give responsiveness to project.

Resource Limitations: Due to limited resource availability, there was difficulty in smooth functioning of project like hand washing liquid and infrastructure. But proper communication and collaboration with Administration this problem is solved. they ensure there will be no scarcity of resource for project.

Issues and Resolutions

Delays in data collection and quality issue in data: Unexpected delays in data collection due to unavailability of staff for questionnaire-based surveys and conducting observational studies due to limited availability of healthcare workers. Its solved by communicating with management and proper deputing staff for data collection on duty working time . giving flexibility of time of collecting data on working time or off working time. Increased communication with HCW for importance of collecting data.

There is also found quality of some data is not adequate and showing inconsistencies and inaccurate. Resolve this issue by proper training on data collection. Quality check and monitoring data collection.

Administration Participation: This is very important issue in progress and development and implementation of project. This was the great concern for project ethical clearance. This issue is

addressed by proper communication with HR head about benefit of project. Why it is necessary for our hospital. what is long term benefit of controlling hospital acquired infections.

Resource Constraint: This was also an initial issue for project progress. But proper communication with finance department this issue is resolve. We got timely all resource material like liquid soap, questionnaire, sanitizers on time¹⁶.

Conclusion

According to data collected and analyzed, report reveals there is variations in knowledge of hand hygiene attitudes, and practices in healthcare workers at Indira Hospital, Supaul.

The analysis of hand hygiene compliance in HCW and healthcare-associated infection (HAI) rates at Indira Hospital for following years 2021 to 2024 shows several key insights.

Positive Trend in Hand Hygiene Compliance: The data shows a consistent increase in hand hygiene compliance rates over the last 3year period and 1st quarter of 2024th we saw 40% compliance rate in 2021, the compliance rate has risen to 56% in 1st quarter of 2024. This trend indicates a PDCA cycle implement by the hospital for promoting and enforcing hand hygiene practices among its staff members done a commendable job [19].

Decreasing HAI Rates: There has been decrease in healthcare-associated infection rates over the last 3 years and this year too in 1st quarter. In the beginning there was 5% HAI rate in 2021, the HAI rate has continuously declined to 4.01% in 1st quarter of 2024. This decline shows a positive correlation between improved hand hygiene compliance and adherence that reduces the incidence of HAI in following consecutive year, reflecting the effectiveness of the hospital's infection control policy and good implementation of PDCA cycle in Indira hospital [18].

Variation in Compliance Among different Staff Categories: Analysis of data also reveals KAP of hand hygiene and compliance rates vary in different categories of staff members¹⁶. While nursing staff shows the highest compliance rate at 58.3%, other categories such as doctors (53.3%), lab technicians and HR staff (57.1%), and other staff (50.8%) also exhibit relatively high compliance rates. This indicates a generally positive adherence to hand hygiene and implementation of PDCA cycle among various departments in the hospital [17].

Room for Improvement: Despite the overall good and positive trend among HCW of Indira hospital there is still some room for implementing PDCA cycle and implementing adherence f hand hygiene compliance, particularly among certain staff categories where compliance rates are slightly

below average. Addressing these areas of lower compliance through targeted education, training, and reinforcement strategies can further overall increase in compliance rates and contribute to decrease HAI.

In conclusion, the data shows positive efforts of Indira Hospital in promoting and implementing hand hygiene practices and knowledge, reducing healthcare-associated infections. The positive trends in hand hygiene compliance and HAI rates show the effectiveness of the hospital's infection control initiatives. In addition, sustained focus on PDCA cycle, education, training, and continuous monitoring will be essential for improvement and maintaining hand hygiene standards, ultimately increasing patient safety and good quality of care at Indira Hospital.

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Glossary

HCW – Health care worker
IPD – In patients department
OPD- Out Patients department

Pts – Patients
HH – Hand hygiene
HAI – Hospital acquired infections